

Formation of wires from bacteria/chloroplasts/water molecules near the cell walls of plant leaves and their roles in imaging and distant information teleportation

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Abstract: Bacterial/chloroplast DNAs are formed from charged particles and by their motions, some currents are emerged. These currents emit some waves. Consequently, bacteria/chloroplasts act like some inductors with two S and N ends. These inductors join to each other from opposite ends and form a wire. This wire is formed near the cellular walls of host cells. Because, there are many ionic and wave channels on these walls and bacterial DNAs could interact with cellular DNAs. Although, in normal conditions, it seems that chloroplasts are distributed within the cell or even near the its center; however, under some conditions like interaction with bacteria, most chloroplasts could move to the cell walls. One can observe the bacterial/chloroplasts wires on the leaf. To this aim, it is sufficient that one closes a leaf to the mouth and put it on a slide of a light microscope. By considering cellular walls, a wire of some bacteria like E.Coli and chloroplasts could be observed. This result could be used in curing diseases and imaging. For example, if one sends some plant cells interior of the body of patient, bacteria could be absorbed by their DNA waves and like a wire could be extracted. Another application could be using of bacterial wire in imaging. One can build a wire of harmless bacteria, send it to the human's body near the damaged cells. Bacterial wires could exchange waves with damaged or cancerous cells and transmit them to the scope very fast. To show the information teleportation between two distant bacteria or cells, we can design an experiment. In this experiment, we put two parts of a plant leaf on two sides of a slide(glass) of microscope and wait for their communications. We can observe that water molecules and bacteria near each plant cell, form several lines. These plant cells aren't in direct contact with each other, however, their lines or wires are related to each other. For example, if in one side, lines are horizontal, in other side, lines are vertical. This means that plant

cells and bacteria interact through glass and by exchanging waves without any direct contact.

Keywords: Wire; Bacteria; Plant Cells; Imaging; Chloroplasts; DNA; Inductors

Introduction:

Recently, it has been shown that some bacteria could transmit electrical signals and act like the wire or cable. For example, one can name cable bacteria which are filamentous bacteria and transmit electricity across distances over 1 cm in sediment and groundwater aquifers. Cable bacteria allow for long distance electron transport, which connects electron donors to electron acceptors [1-3]. This property may be observed in other bacteria with low density. Besides these researches, many scientists have shown that bacteria could exchange electromagnetic waves with medium. In one work, authors have argued that anode-respiring bacteria (ARB) in a biofilm anode carry out an oxidation half-reaction of organic matter, producing an electrical current from renewable biomass, including wastes. At the same time, ARB produce protons, usually one proton for every electron. They have shown that how current density generated by an acclimated ARB biofilm was limited by proton transport out of the biofilm [4]. Another group have argued that extremely low frequency (<300 Hz) electromagnetic fields (ELF-EMF) induces a decrease in growth rate and morphological changes for both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria [5]. Another scientists have discussed that millimeter waves affected *Escherichia coli* and many other bacteria, mainly depressing their growth and changing properties and activity. These effects were non-thermal and depended on different factors. In their work, the significant cellular targets for wave effects were water, cell plasma membrane, and genome [6]. Other investigators have worked on magnetotactic bacteria (MTB) which have the unique ability to produce magnetic particles surrounded by a biomembrane to form the magnetosome organelle. They have argued that these bacteria have novel physical and magnetic properties and have consequently been used in several biotechnological applications [7,8]. In addition to bacteria, chloroplasts also have DNAs and genetic matters and could emit or receive electromagnetic waves. Chloroplasts play a central role in plant defense and are targeted by pathogen effectors [9]. They could exchange waves with each other and bacteria and control infectious diseases. Considering interactions between chloroplasts and bacteria may help us to understand bioelectrical engineering of cells [10]. Furthermore, the role of water molecules shouldn't be ignored. Because, molecules of waters could help in exchanging waves between bacteria, chloroplasts and cells and formation of bacterial/cellular wires [11,12]. Motivated by these researches, we consider the

probability for formation of bacterial/chloroplast wires near the cell walls of a plant leaf. We also discuss about some of applications of bacteria wires in imaging.

The outline of paper is as follows: In section II, we propose the method. Section III shows the result and in section IV, we show that bacterial wires and plant cells could exchange information through a glass and without any contact. In section V discusses about applications of bacterial wire. The last section is devoted to conclusion.

II. Material and Method

II-A: Material:

In this research, we have used of below matters:

1. Bacteria
2. Plant leaf
3. A light microscope
4. Slides

II-B: Method:

1. Bacteria have at least two types of genetic matters: Plasmids and bacterial DNAs. Each DNA has been formed from charged particles and by its motion, charges move and a current is emerged. These currents emit some special waves. Thus, bacterial DNAs and plasmids emit waves. In fact, bacterial genetic matters may act like some inductors with two ends S and N. End of S from each bacteria absorbs end of N. Thus, two bacteria acts like two couple inductors. If bacteria become close to each other, form a line of coupled inductors. On the hand, cellular DNAs also send some waves. Consequently, bacteria and cells exchange waves and absorb each other. This causes that a wire of bacteria is formed near the cell walls (See Figure 1).
2. We can separate a part of a leaf and put it on the slide. Then, we can put close the leaf section to the mouth and waite that bubble circuits within saliva which act like the electrical circuits, exchange waves with leaf cells.

These waves could help the bacteria which transform from the mouth to the leaf easily.

3. We put the slide under the microscope

4. We consider the interaction between bacteria, chloroplasts and the place of their colonies (See Figure 2).

Fig 1: Exchanging waves between bacterial and cellular DNAs and formation of a wire

Fig 2: Transformation of bacteria and bubble waves within saliva from mouth to the leaf

III. Results:

In this research, we have used of several leaves like the ones in figure 3. Without transferring bacteria from the mouth to the leaf, cell walls are empty (See figure 4). After transferring bacteria, plant cells, chloroplasts and other elements of plant leaf interact with bacteria and control their behavior. Some of these interactions are presented in figures 5 -7. Naturally, bacteria and chloroplasts form a wire. This is because that their genetic matters exchange waves with each other and act like the coupled inductors. Consequently, magnetic fields could enter from one end of inductor and go out from another end. One end could be known as S and another end could be known as S. All N ends like to be in closed to the S ends and this causes that several lines of bacteria or chloroplasts are formed (See figure 8). On the other hand, bacteria and chloroplasts like to form a wire near the cell walls and compete with each other to overcome the cell line (See figures 9-12). This is because that cell walls have ioninc and wave channels or receptors which DNA waves could be transformed through them and interact with bacterial/chloroplasts DNAs. Thus, bacteria/chloroplasts tend to make a colony near the cell walls. Consequently, a wire of bacteria/chloroplasts is formed.

Fig 3: A leaf we have used in experiment

Fig 4: Cell walls without bacteria and chloroplast

Fig 5: Interact between bacteria and chloroplasts (First Picture)

Fig 6: Interaction between bacteria and chloroplasts (Second picture)

Fig 7: Interaction between bacteria and chloroplasts (Third picture)

Fig 8: A wire of bacteria and chloroplasts (First picture)

Fig 9: A wire of bacteria and chloroplast along cell walls (Second picture).

Fig 10: A wire of bacteria and chloroplasts near the cell walls (Third picture)

Fig 11: A wire of bacteria and chloroplasts near the cell walls (Forth picture)

Fig 12: A wire of bacteria and chloroplasts near the cell walls (Five Picture)

IV: Teleporting of information between distant cells/bacteria

Until now, we have considered the process of formation of bacterial/chloroplast wires near the cell walls. Now, we can assert that cells and bacteria could interact

by exchanging waves and without any direct contact. To this aim, we put two parts of a leaf on two sides of a slide which its genus is of a type of glass. Then, we put this glass under the microscope. By changing the location of the lens, first, we observe the leaf on first side and consider its bacterial and water lines. Then, we change the place of the lens and observe the second part of leaf on other side of slide (See figure 13). It is interesting that in first side, lines are mostly vertical (See figure 14), while in second side, lines are mostly horizontal (See figure 15). Maybe, the reason is the states of cells. In figure 14, it could be seen that triangle parts of pentagonal/hexagonal plant cells are vertical and in parallel to lines. In figure 15, reverse, triangle parts of pentagonal/hexagonal plant cells are horizontal and again in parallel to their lines. Thus, plant cells control the process of formation of wires and provide the needed devices for distant information teleportation.

Fig 13: Bacterial wires on two sides of a slide under microscope

Fig 14: Bacterial/water wires along plant cells (vertical)

Fig 15: Bacterial/water wires along cell lines (horizontal)

V. Discussion:

In this research, we have shown that bacteria could act like the coupled inductors which form a line near the cell walls. This is because that their DNAs act like the inductors and exchange waves with each other and DNA inductors of a plant cell. We can use of this mechanism in curing diseases. We can send plant cells within the body and absorb bacteria by them. For this aim, the exchanged waves with

plant cells and bacteria should be more than exchanged waves between human host cells and bacteria (See figure 16).

Exchanged waves between bacteria and host cells << exchanged waves between bacteria and plant cells

In addition to this application, we can build bacteria wires and use of them in micro and nano-technology. For example, we can build some bacterial wires from some harmless bacteria, send them into human body and diagnose some diseases like cancers. Because, bacteria exchange waves with cells and transmit information very fast (See figure 17).

Fig 16: Using of plant cells in absorbing bacteria

Fig 17: Using of bacterial wire in imaging

V. Conclusion:

In this research, we have shown that bacteria/chloroplasts act like some coupled inductors and form a wire near the gates of host cells. To show this, we have used of a leaf and close it to the mouth. Consequently, some bacteria were transformed from mouth to the leaf and were considered under a microscope. It was observed that bacteria/chloroplasts form a wire near the cell walls of the leaf. In fact, cell walls have some gates which exchange DNA waves of host cells with bacteria and absorb or repel them. Also, bacterial DNAs emit some waves which could be taken by another bacterial DNAs and cellular ones. These waves help the bacteria to

form a wire. We can use of this event in curing diseases and imaging. We can build a wire of harmless bacteria and send it a target cell interior of body to analyze evolutions of cancers and other damaged cells. To assert the information teleportation between distant bacterial wires and plant cells, we put two parts of leaf on two sides of a slide and put them under microscope. It was interesting that several wires of water molecules and bacteria were formed that be in related to each other. This means that bacteria and cells could exchange information by waves.

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